

Distributed Cooperative Control of Quadrotor Formations via Lyapunov Transformations

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Abstract: This paper develops a non-linear distributed feedback control strategy for formation trajectory tracking of multi-quadrotor systems. Sufficient conditions for closed-loop stability are formulated in terms of the stability margin of the individual vehicles and the information flow among agents. The design exploits Lyapunov transformations that recast the non-linear dynamics into equivalent Linear Time Invariant (LTI) representations, without local linearization, thereby enabling the use of linear analysis and synthesis tools. The resulting controller ensures stable formation tracking of constant-velocity references with zero steady-state error and rejection of constant wind disturbances.

Keywords: Consensus, Control of networks, Distributed non-linear control, Multi-agent systems, Lyapunov methods

1. INTRODUCTION

With the continuing development of autonomous-vehicle technology, multi-vehicle applications are becoming increasingly relevant in several domains. Robust control methods for these systems are therefore of particular interest, since dynamically decoupled vehicles, each with limited information about the overall group, must act in a coordinated manner.

Classical solutions have often followed either a "leader-follower" or a "virtual leader" architecture because of their simplicity. For example, in Pereira et al. (2017), a trajectory planner was proposed for a group of autonomous vehicles following a common leader. However, limitations in group performance and computational load have motivated the study of richer communication structures and more general distributed-control strategies. In particular, graph-theoretic consensus methods have become a powerful framework for cooperative control, since they enable the design of global coordination laws based on local interactions among neighbouring agents Fax and Murray (2004), Olfati-Saber and Murray (2004), Olfati-Saber, R., Fax, J.A. and Murray, R.M. (2007), both in linear and non-linear dynamic models.

Greater cooperation between vehicles alleviates the individual computational burden while enhancing robustness against external factors that may affect the information flow within the group, paving the way for more complex applications with an increasing number of vehicles. For instance, robust distributed consensus control for large-scale drone swarms was explored in Chen et al. (2020) and a decentralized controller for multi-quadrotor systems was proposed by Toksöz et al. (2019), which ensures trajectory tracking with collision avoidance between vehicles.

Naturally, the design of group-control solutions must be coupled with a careful stability analysis of each individual vehicle. This paper builds on the quadrotor-control methodology developed in Madeiras, J., Cardeira, C. and Oliveira, P. (2024), where non-linear Lyapunov transformations, in the sense of Brockett (1970), were used to rewrite the non-linear model as an equivalent linear model without approximation. The main contribution of this work is to extend this methodology to multi-quadrotor systems, ensuring distributed position tracking for the formation while exploiting the full vehicle dynamics. The proposed methodology is also conceived with practical implementation in mind and is kept as general as possible. Although the application considered here focuses on multi-quadrotor systems, the proposed framework can, in principle, be extended to broader classes of multi-agent systems, including those composed of agents with heterogeneous dynamics.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the model and problem statement. Section 3 recalls the consensus tools required for the distributed controller. Section 4 presents the formation and attitude controllers. Section 5 reports simulations, and Section 6 concludes the paper.

NOTATION

In this paper, vectors are denoted by bold lower-case letters (e.g. \mathbf{u} , \mathbf{x}), matrices by bold upper-case letters (e.g. \mathbf{R} , \mathbf{L}) and the i -th element of a vector is denoted \mathbf{x}_i . The symbol $\mathbf{0}$ denotes a zero matrix, of appropriate dimensions, and \mathbf{I}_n represents an $n \times n$ identity matrix. Furthermore, the unit vectors aligned with the x, y and z axes are, respectively, \mathbf{e}_1 , \mathbf{e}_2 and \mathbf{e}_3 . The time derivative of a quantity s is denoted by \dot{s} and $\|\mathbf{x}\|$ denotes the Euclidean

norm of vector $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$. In \mathbb{R}^3 , $[\mathbf{v}\times]$ denotes the skew-symmetric matrix associated with a generic vector \mathbf{v} as

$$[\mathbf{v}\times] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -v_3 & v_2 \\ v_3 & 0 & -v_1 \\ -v_2 & v_1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The notation $\{E\}$ represents a generic coordinate frame and, in particular, $\{I\}$ denotes the inertial frame of reference and $\{B\}$ denotes the vehicle's body frame. Finally, the symbol \otimes denotes the Kronecker product between matrices and, for a succession of k square matrices $\mathbf{A}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $\hat{\mathbf{A}} \in \mathbb{R}^{kn \times kn}$ is defined as

$$\hat{\mathbf{A}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_1 & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{A}_k \end{bmatrix}.$$

2. PROBLEM FORMULATION

2.1 Quadrotor dynamics and kinematics

Consider the quadrotor vehicle model represented in Fig. 1. It is equipped with four identical motors and propellers symmetrically distributed along the body, which generate thrust forces and reaction torques normal to the rotor planes. Differential rotations of the motors allow the generation of torques in the three axes of the body frame of the vehicle, located at its centre of mass. The differential equations that describe the kinematics and dynamics of this vehicle, with possible wind perturbations, are defined as

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\mathbf{p}} = \mathbf{R}\mathbf{v} \\ \dot{\mathbf{v}} = -[\boldsymbol{\omega}\times]\mathbf{v} - \frac{T}{m}\mathbf{e}_3 + \mathbf{R}^T(g\mathbf{e}_3 + \mathbf{f}_D + \mathbf{d}) \\ \dot{\mathbf{q}} = \frac{1}{2}\boldsymbol{\Xi}(\mathbf{q})\boldsymbol{\omega} \\ \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}} = -\mathbf{J}^{-1}[\boldsymbol{\omega}\times]\mathbf{J}\boldsymbol{\omega} + \mathbf{J}^{-1}\boldsymbol{\tau} \end{cases}, \quad (1)$$

where $m \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ is the total mass, $\mathbf{J} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ is the inertia matrix with respect to $\{B\}$, g is the gravitational acceleration, $\mathbf{R} \in \text{SO}(3)$ is the rotation matrix from $\{B\}$ to $\{I\}$, $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the inertial position of the centre of mass in $\{I\}$, $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the velocity of the centre of mass relative to $\{I\}$, expressed in $\{B\}$, and $\mathbf{q} = [\mathbf{q}_v^T q_0]^T \in \{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^4 : \|\mathbf{x}\| = 1\}$ is the unit quaternion that describes the attitude of the vehicle, with \mathbf{q}_v being its imaginary vector and q_0 its real component. Furthermore, $\boldsymbol{\omega} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ denotes the angular velocity relative to $\{I\}$, expressed in $\{B\}$; \mathbf{f}_D is the drag force per unit mass written in $\{I\}$; $\mathbf{d} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the wind perturbation expressed in $\{I\}$; $T \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ is the total generated thrust; $\boldsymbol{\tau} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the total generated torque expressed in $\{B\}$; and $\boldsymbol{\Xi}(\mathbf{q}) = \begin{bmatrix} q_0\mathbf{I}_3 + [\mathbf{q}_v \times] \\ -\mathbf{q}_v^T \end{bmatrix}$.

2.2 Problem formulation

Consider a set of n identical quadrotor vehicles, each with individual dynamics described in (1). Suppose that each vehicle measures the relative position of a subset of other vehicles, effectively establishing an information graph $G = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{A})$. Here, \mathcal{V} is the set of vertices v_i in the graph and \mathcal{E} is the set of edges (v_i, v_j) . The scalar $a_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ denotes the weight of the edge (v_i, v_j) , and $\mathcal{A} = [a_{ij}]$ is the adjacency matrix of the graph. Without loss of generality, it is assumed that there are no self-loops, that is, $a_{ii} = 0, i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$.

Fig. 1. Diagram of the quadrotor

The objective is to design a controller for each vehicle that achieves formation tracking of a prescribed trajectory \mathbf{p}_d and heading angle ψ_d , while rejecting constant wind perturbations. Additionally, assume that each vehicle i is equipped with a sensor set that accurately measures, in real time, the relative position of each neighbouring vehicle j , $(\mathbf{p}_j - \mathbf{p}_i)$, its velocity \mathbf{v}_i , its attitude \mathbf{q}_i and its angular velocity $\boldsymbol{\omega}_i$. In commercially available quadrotors, these quantities can be obtained from onboard motion sensors. In particular, GPS can be used to obtain relative positions and velocities, while inertial measurement units can be used to determine attitude and angular velocity (Gamage, K., Lee, T. and Snyder, M. (2021)). To guarantee a well-posed control law, assume that the angular velocities $\boldsymbol{\omega}_i$ and angular accelerations $\dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}}_i$, with $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, are bounded signals.

3. CONSENSUS THEORY

Consider an algebraic directed graph $G_x = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{A}, \mathbf{x})$ consisting of n nodes, with $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}$, $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ denoting the value of node v_i . It is said that the nodes reach a consensus when $\mathbf{x}_i = \mathbf{x}_j$, for all $i \neq j$. Define the out-strength of node v_i as

$$\text{str}_{out}(v_i) = \sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij}. \quad (2)$$

The *strength matrix* is defined as $\boldsymbol{\Delta} = \text{diag}(\text{str}_{out}(v_i))$. The *Laplacian matrix* associated with G_x is then

$$\mathbf{L} = \boldsymbol{\Delta} - \mathcal{A}. \quad (3)$$

Remark 1. By construction, all the elements of each row of \mathbf{L} sum to zero. Therefore, \mathbf{L} has a null eigenvalue corresponding to the eigenvector $\mathbf{w} = [1 \dots 1]^T$. In other words, the rank of \mathbf{L} is lower than n .

A graph is said to be *strongly connected* if and only if every pair of nodes in the graph can be connected via a path that respects the orientation of the edges. In Olfati-Saber and Murray (2004), a very important conclusion is proven in the case of strongly connected graphs.

Theorem 1. Let $G = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{A})$ be a weighted directed graph with Laplacian \mathbf{L} . If G is strongly connected, then $\text{rank}(\mathbf{L}) = n - 1$. More generally, $\text{rank}(\mathbf{L}) = n - 1$ holds whenever the directed graph contains a spanning tree.

Another useful result, based on the Geršgorin disk theorem and stated in Olfati-Saber and Murray (2004), is also presented.

Theorem 2. Consider a weighted directed graph $G = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{A})$ with Laplacian \mathbf{L} , and define $s_{max}(G) =$

$\max_i \text{str}_{out}(v_i)$, with $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. Then all the eigenvalues of \mathbf{L} are located in the following disk

$$D(G) = \{z \in \mathbb{C} : |z - s_{max}(G)| \leq s_{max}(G)\} \quad (4)$$

Consensus can be enforced by a control law that uses information from neighbouring agents through the Laplacian matrix. For agents with pure integral dynamics, the following result is obtained.

Theorem 3. Consider a strongly connected algebraic graph $G_x = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{A}, \mathbf{x})$ with n nodes and a corresponding Laplacian matrix \mathbf{L} . Suppose that each value \mathbf{x}_i , with $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, evolves according to

$$\frac{d^m \mathbf{x}_i}{dt^m} = \mathbf{u}_i, \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{u}_i is the input of node i . The control law

$$\mathbf{u} = -\mathbf{L}\mathbf{x}, \quad (6)$$

places the eigenvalues of the system at the roots of $\lambda^m = -\lambda_L$, that is,

$$\lambda_k = |\lambda_L|^{1/m} \exp\left(\frac{i(\arg(-\lambda_L) + 2k\pi)}{m}\right), \quad (7)$$

for $k \in \{0, \dots, m-1\}$.

Proof. With this control law, the full dynamics of the whole graph, described by the vector

$$\mathbf{x}_f = \left[\mathbf{x}^T, \frac{d\mathbf{x}^T}{dt}, \dots, \frac{d^{m-1}\mathbf{x}^T}{dt^{m-1}} \right]^T, \quad (8)$$

can be written as

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_f = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I}_n & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I}_n & \dots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{I}_n \\ -\mathbf{L} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_f \equiv \mathbf{M}\mathbf{x}_f. \quad (9)$$

To evaluate the eigenvalues of \mathbf{M} , use Schur's determinant formula. Writing $\mathbf{M} - \lambda \mathbf{I}_{kn}$, with $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}$, as a block matrix $\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P} & \mathbf{Q} \\ \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{S} \end{bmatrix}$, with \mathbf{S} invertible, gives

$$\det(\mathbf{M} - \lambda \mathbf{I}_{mn}) = \det(\mathbf{S}) \det(\mathbf{P} - \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{S}^{-1}\mathbf{R}). \quad (10)$$

Choosing

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{P} = \begin{bmatrix} -\lambda \mathbf{I}_n & \mathbf{I}_n & \dots & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & -\lambda \mathbf{I}_n & \mathbf{I}_n \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} & -\lambda \mathbf{I}_n \end{bmatrix}, \\ \mathbf{Q} = [\mathbf{0} \dots \mathbf{I}_n]^T \\ \mathbf{R} = [-\mathbf{L} \dots \mathbf{0}] \\ \mathbf{S} = -\lambda \mathbf{I}_n \end{array} \right., \quad (11)$$

and repeatedly applying Schur's formula, the determinant is found to be

$$\det(\mathbf{M} - \lambda \mathbf{I}_{mn}) = \det(-\mathbf{L} - \lambda^m \mathbf{I}_n). \quad (12)$$

Let λ_L denote an eigenvalue of \mathbf{L} . Setting the above determinant equal to zero gives the eigenvalues of \mathbf{M} through $\lambda^m = -\lambda_L$, or equivalently

$$\lambda_k = |\lambda_L|^{1/m} \exp\left(\frac{i(\arg(-\lambda_L) + 2k\pi)}{m}\right), \quad (13)$$

for $k \in \{0, \dots, m-1\}$. \square

Notice that this control law leads to an unstable closed-loop system for $m > 2$ and, for $m = 2$, it is at best

marginally stable when the eigenvalues of \mathbf{L} are real, which is not guaranteed for directed graphs. This is relevant here because position consensus with acceleration-level actuation resembles the case $m = 2$. Moreover, adding integral action on the position error to improve tracking performance yields a third-order consensus structure, and the resulting closed-loop system would be unstable in the absence of sufficient internal damping.

However, the vehicles are not pure integrators and, although the position states need to be controlled cooperatively, the velocity control can be handled individually. If the vehicles provide sufficient internal velocity damping, then the stability margin of the inner loop can compensate for the destabilizing modes introduced by the outer-loop formation controller. This raises the question of the stability margin of the closed-loop system, which motivates the following theorem.

Theorem 4. Consider an exponentially stable dynamic system, $\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$, that admits a Lyapunov function $V(\mathbf{x})$ that satisfies

- (1) $V(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{P} \mathbf{x}$, with \mathbf{P} symmetric positive definite;
- (2) $\dot{V}(\mathbf{x}) \leq -\alpha V(\mathbf{x})$, $\forall \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, with $\alpha > 0$.

Consider as well the linear system $\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}$. The sum of these dynamics,

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}, \quad (14)$$

is exponentially stable if $\lambda_{max}(\mathbf{P}\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{P}) < \alpha \lambda_{min}(\mathbf{P})$, where $\lambda_{min}(\mathbf{Q})$ and $\lambda_{max}(\mathbf{Q})$ denote, respectively, the minimum and maximum eigenvalues of matrix \mathbf{Q} .

Proof. Using the same Lyapunov function, $V(\mathbf{x})$, with these new dynamics, the time derivative becomes

$$\dot{V}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{P} \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) + \mathbf{f}^T(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{P} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{x}^T (\mathbf{P}\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{P}) \mathbf{x}. \quad (15)$$

From the second condition for $V(\mathbf{x})$ and noting that $\mathbf{P}\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{P}$ is symmetric,

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}(\mathbf{x}) &\leq -\alpha \mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{P} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{x}^T (\mathbf{P}\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{P}) \mathbf{x} \\ &\leq -\alpha \lambda_{min}(\mathbf{P}) \|\mathbf{x}\|^2 + \lambda_{max}(\mathbf{P}\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{P}) \|\mathbf{x}\|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Thus, this system is exponentially stable if

$$\lambda_{max}(\mathbf{P}\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{P}) - \alpha \lambda_{min}(\mathbf{P}) < 0. \quad (17)$$

\square

Note that \mathbf{A} does not need to be Hurwitz for the condition of this theorem to hold. The symmetric contribution $\lambda_{max}(\mathbf{P}\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{P})$ may be positive, provided that it is dominated by the exponential decay rate of the nominal dynamics. When the internal node dynamics are linear, a more practical sufficient condition follows.

Theorem 5. Consider two dynamic systems $\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}$ and $\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{x}$, and define $\mathbf{Q}_A = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{A}^T)$ and $\mathbf{Q}_B = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{B} + \mathbf{B}^T)$. The system

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = (\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{B})\mathbf{x} \quad (18)$$

is exponentially stable if $\lambda_{max}(\mathbf{Q}_A) + \lambda_{max}(\mathbf{Q}_B) < 0$.

Proof. Denote by λ_i the eigenvalues of $\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{B}$ and by \mathbf{v}_i the corresponding unit eigenvectors. It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}e(\lambda_i) &= \left\langle \frac{\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{B} + (\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{B})^T}{2} \mathbf{v}_i, \mathbf{v}_i \right\rangle \\ &= \langle \mathbf{Q}_A \mathbf{v}_i, \mathbf{v}_i \rangle + \langle \mathbf{Q}_B \mathbf{v}_i, \mathbf{v}_i \rangle \\ &\leq \lambda_{max}(\mathbf{Q}_A) + \lambda_{max}(\mathbf{Q}_B). \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Therefore, if $\lambda_{max}(\mathbf{Q}_A) + \lambda_{max}(\mathbf{Q}_B) < 0$, the eigenvalues of the system are guaranteed to have a negative real part. \square

The main conclusion drawn from this section is that the distributed controller may be designed modularly, with an outer loop responsible for consensus among agents and individual inner loops that stabilize other internal states, such as the velocity in the quadrotor case. However, although the loops can be made separate, they cannot be designed independently, since it is the internal damping of the vehicles that determines the stability margins of the overall formation controller.

As a last remark, note that the overall performance for the group agreement task is related to the eigenvalue of \mathbf{L} with the smallest real part (different from 0). This eigenvalue can be shown to be larger for denser networks and smaller for sparser ones (Olfati-Saber and Murray (2004)).

4. CONTROLLER DESIGN

Motivated by the previous section, this section derives a non-linear control law that makes the quadrotor formation track a desired trajectory, reject constant wind disturbances, and achieve zero steady-state error for constant-velocity references. The controller has an inner component that stabilizes each vehicle and an outer distributed component that coordinates the vehicle positions using the available inter-agent communication. Through non-linear Lyapunov transformations (Brockett (1970)), the dynamic model is written in an equivalent linear form, allowing the use of standard linear techniques.

4.1 Position Tracking Control

Suppose the vehicles communicate with one another according to a strongly connected algebraic graph $G_p = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{A}, \mathbf{p})$ with an associated Laplacian matrix \mathbf{L} , where \mathbf{p} collects the position vectors of all vehicles in the formation. To ensure tracking, imagine the presence of a "virtual" vehicle, which follows the desired trajectory perfectly and broadcasts its position in real time to a subset of vehicles. This creates a new information graph based on the previous one, $G'_p = (\mathcal{V}', \mathcal{E}', \mathcal{A}', \mathbf{p})$, with

$$\mathcal{A}' = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} & b_1 \\ a_{21} & 0 & \dots & a_{2n} & b_2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & \dots & 0 & b_n \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (20)$$

where the values $b_i \geq 0$ are the pinning gains that connect the virtual vehicle to the vehicles in the formation, with at least one of them being strictly positive. Throughout the paper, the convention $a_{ij} > 0$ means that vehicle i has access to the relative position of vehicle j ; therefore, the i -th row of \mathcal{A} contains the neighbours used by vehicle i . The error vector for the i -th vehicle may be defined as

$$\Delta \mathbf{p}_i = \sum_{j=1}^n (a_{ij}(\mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{p}_j - \mathbf{h}_{ij}) + b_i(\mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{p}_d - \mathbf{h}_{id})) \quad (21)$$

where \mathbf{p}_d is the desired trajectory. Vectors \mathbf{h}_{ij} represent an offset that should exist between the i -th and the j -th vehicle, and vector \mathbf{h}_{id} is the offset that should exist between the i -th vehicle and the virtual vehicle. These vectors may be interpreted as the relative positions that the vehicles should maintain at steady state, thus conveying the shape of the formation throughout time.

Concatenating these vectors into a single one, $\Delta \mathbf{p} = [\Delta \mathbf{p}_1^T \dots \Delta \mathbf{p}_n^T]^T$, leads to

$$\Delta \mathbf{p} = (\mathbf{L}' \otimes \mathbf{I}_3) \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{h} - (\mathbf{b} \otimes \mathbf{I}_3) \mathbf{p}_d \equiv \mathbf{L}'_3 \mathbf{p} - \Delta \mathbf{p}_{ref}. \quad (22)$$

Here, \mathbf{L}' denotes the Laplacian matrix of the graph G'_p without the row and column referring to the virtual vehicle. This matrix is constructed from the Laplacian matrix of G_p , \mathbf{L} , as

$$\mathbf{L}' = \mathbf{L} + \begin{bmatrix} b_1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & b_n \end{bmatrix}. \quad (23)$$

The Kronecker product accounts for the three-dimensional position vector. Finally, the vector \mathbf{h} concatenates all the offsets for a particular vehicle, with

$$\mathbf{h}_i = \sum_{j=1}^n (a_{ij} \mathbf{h}_{ij} + b_i \mathbf{h}_{id}). \quad (24)$$

Remark 2. Under the assumed strong connectivity of G_p and with at least one strictly positive pinning gain b_i , the pinned Laplacian \mathbf{L}' is nonsingular. Equivalently, the null eigenvalue present in \mathbf{L} by construction is removed once the reference information is introduced. That null eigenvalue represents the fact that, in the absence of absolute reference information, the consensus value was not prescribed. Once such information is available, the consensus value is prescribed by the reference.

Remark 3. By construction, the matrix \mathbf{L}'_3 will have the same eigenvalues as \mathbf{L}' , each with an algebraic multiplicity of 3.

Define an integral state $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ such that $\dot{\boldsymbol{\eta}} = \Delta \mathbf{p}$. Using the first two equations of (1) and defining $\mathbf{u}_i = -\frac{T_i}{m} \mathbf{e}_3 + \mathbf{R}_i^T (g \mathbf{e}_3 + \mathbf{f}_D)$, the full dynamics of the drone formation can be written as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{v}} \\ \Delta \dot{\mathbf{p}} \\ \dot{\boldsymbol{\eta}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -[\boldsymbol{\omega} \times] & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{L}'_3 \hat{\mathbf{R}} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I}_{3n} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v} \\ \Delta \mathbf{p} \\ \boldsymbol{\eta} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{3n} \\ \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{u} \\ + \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{R}}^T \\ \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{d} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{I}_{3n} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \Delta \dot{\mathbf{p}}_{ref}. \quad (25)$$

Consider the following coordinate transformation, inspired in the one proposed in Madeiras, J., Cardeira, C. and Oliveira, P. (2024)

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_v \\ \mathbf{x}_p \\ \mathbf{x}_\eta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{R}} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I}_{3n} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I}_{3n} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v} \\ \Delta \mathbf{p} \\ \boldsymbol{\eta} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (26)$$

This transformation matrix is nonsingular for all attitudes, has a continuous time derivative, and has unit determinant. In particular, the term $-\boldsymbol{\omega}_i \times \mathbf{v}_i$ is cancelled by the time derivative of $\mathbf{R}_i \mathbf{v}_i$, since $\dot{\mathbf{R}}_i = \mathbf{R}_i [\boldsymbol{\omega}_i \times]$. Hence, this transformation is a valid Lyapunov transformation. Note that this transformation depends only on the individual attitude measurements of the vehicles. The transformed system has the following dynamics,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{x}}_v \\ \dot{\mathbf{x}}_p \\ \dot{\mathbf{x}}_\eta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{L}'_3 & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I}_{3n} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_v \\ \mathbf{x}_p \\ \mathbf{x}_\eta \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{R}} \\ \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{u} \\ + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{3n} \\ \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{d} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{I}_{3n} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \Delta \dot{\mathbf{p}}_{ref}. \quad (27)$$

Following the logic of the previous section, an inner controller is chosen for each vehicle using velocity feedback,

$$\hat{\mathbf{R}}\mathbf{u}_{inner} = -\hat{\mathbf{K}}_v\mathbf{x}_v. \quad (28)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{K}}_v$ is positive definite. An outer loop using only position and integral-error feedback is chosen as

$$\hat{\mathbf{R}}\mathbf{u}_{outer} = -\hat{\mathbf{K}}_p\mathbf{x}_p - \hat{\mathbf{K}}_\eta\mathbf{x}_\eta, \quad (29)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{K}}_p$ and $\hat{\mathbf{K}}_\eta$ are positive definite. Therefore, consider the control law

$$\mathbf{u} = - \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{R}}^T \hat{\mathbf{K}}_v & \hat{\mathbf{R}}^T \hat{\mathbf{K}}_p & \hat{\mathbf{R}}^T \hat{\mathbf{K}}_\eta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_v \\ \mathbf{x}_p \\ \mathbf{x}_\eta \end{bmatrix}. \quad (30)$$

Using this control law in system (27), it can be shown that the closed-loop eigenvalues of the whole formation are the solutions of

$$\det \left(\lambda^3 \mathbf{I}_{3n} + \lambda^2 \hat{\mathbf{K}}_v + \lambda \hat{\mathbf{K}}_p \mathbf{L}'_3 + \hat{\mathbf{K}}_\eta \mathbf{L}'_3 \right) = 0. \quad (31)$$

In general, computing the closed-loop eigenvalues requires solving the above characteristic equation directly, which may be computationally demanding for formations with many vehicles. From the dynamics in system (27), it follows that the motion along the three axes is decoupled, thus the individual gain matrices \mathbf{K}_{v_i} , \mathbf{K}_{p_i} and \mathbf{K}_{η_i} can be made diagonal. A special case arises if, for each axis of motion, the feedback gains are equal for all vehicles. In that case, (31) simplifies to

$$P_x(\lambda)P_y(\lambda)P_z(\lambda) = 0, \quad (32)$$

with

$$P_x(\lambda) = \prod_{i=1}^n \left(\lambda^3 + k_{v_x} \lambda^2 + \lambda \lambda_{L'_i} k_{p_x} + \lambda_{L'_i} k_{\eta_x} \right) \quad (33)$$

with $P_y(\lambda)$ and $P_z(\lambda)$ defined analogously. In the definition of the polynomials, $\lambda_{L'_i}$ denotes the i -th eigenvalue of \mathbf{L}' , which has a positive real part under the pinning assumptions stated above, but may be complex. Write $\lambda_{L'_i} = a_i + ib_i$, with $a_i > 0$. In this case, the generalized Routh-Hurwitz criterion for complex polynomials may be used to infer sufficient and necessary conditions for these polynomials to be Hurwitz stable (see Hastir and Muolo (2023)). These conditions are

$$\begin{cases} k_{v_x}, k_{v_y}, k_{v_z}, k_{p_x}, k_{p_y}, k_{p_z}, k_{\eta_x}, k_{\eta_y}, k_{\eta_z} > 0 \\ k_{v_x} > \frac{k_{\eta_x}}{k_{p_x}} + \frac{b_i^2 k_{p_x}}{a_i k_{v_x}}, \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\} \\ k_{v_y} > \frac{k_{\eta_y}}{k_{p_y}} + \frac{b_i^2 k_{p_y}}{a_i k_{v_y}}, \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\} \\ k_{v_z} > \frac{k_{\eta_z}}{k_{p_z}} + \frac{b_i^2 k_{p_z}}{a_i k_{v_z}}, \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\} \end{cases} \quad (34)$$

These results are consistent with the conclusions of Section 3. Integral action introduces potentially destabilizing third-order consensus modes and, when the eigenvalues of \mathbf{L}' are complex, the proportional gain also affects the stability margin through the imaginary part of the graph eigenvalues. The damping introduced by the individual derivative gains is therefore essential to render the overall closed-loop system stable; larger derivative gains increase the admissible range of proportional and integral gains.

Once stability is guaranteed, the following lemma establishes the steady-state properties relevant to the tracking problem.

Lemma 1. Consider the control law applied to the system (25)

$$\mathbf{u} = - \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{R}}^T \hat{\mathbf{K}}_v & \hat{\mathbf{R}}^T \hat{\mathbf{K}}_p & \hat{\mathbf{R}}^T \hat{\mathbf{K}}_\eta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_v \\ \mathbf{x}_p \\ \mathbf{x}_\eta \end{bmatrix}, \quad (35)$$

with $\hat{\mathbf{K}}_v$, $\hat{\mathbf{K}}_p$ and $\hat{\mathbf{K}}_\eta$ chosen so that the closed-loop system is stable. It follows that:

- (1) The control law rejects the effects of constant disturbances \mathbf{d} on the velocity and the position of every vehicle;
- (2) The control law allows the tracking of a ramp signal in $\Delta \mathbf{p}_{ref}$ with zero steady-state error in every vehicle.

Proof. Applying the control law in (27) and performing the Laplace transform leads to a system of equations written as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_v(s) \\ \mathbf{x}_p(s) \\ \mathbf{x}_\eta(s) \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{M}(s)^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{3n} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & s\mathbf{I}_{3n} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{d}(s) \\ \Delta \mathbf{p}_{ref}(s) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (36)$$

with

$$\mathbf{M}(s) = \begin{bmatrix} s\mathbf{I}_{3n} + \hat{\mathbf{K}}_v & \hat{\mathbf{K}}_p & \hat{\mathbf{K}}_\eta \\ -\mathbf{L}'_3 & s\mathbf{I}_{3n} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{I}_{3n} & s\mathbf{I}_{3n} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (37)$$

The final value theorem states that, if the system is stable,

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_v(t) \\ \mathbf{x}_p(t) \\ \mathbf{x}_\eta(t) \end{bmatrix} = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} s \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_v(s) \\ \mathbf{x}_p(s) \\ \mathbf{x}_\eta(s) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (38)$$

For a constant disturbance $\mathbf{d}(s) = \mathbf{c}_d/s$ and a ramp reference $\Delta \mathbf{p}_{ref}(s) = \mathbf{c}_p/s^2$, where \mathbf{c}_d and \mathbf{c}_p are constant vectors, substitution in (36) gives

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 0} s \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_v(s) \\ \mathbf{x}_p(s) \\ \mathbf{x}_\eta(s) \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{M}(0)^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{3n} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I}_{3n} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{c}_d \\ \mathbf{c}_p \end{bmatrix}. \quad (39)$$

Using Schur's formula, one can compute

$$\mathbf{M}(0)^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{L}'_3^{-1} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{I}_{3n} \\ \hat{\mathbf{K}}_\eta^{-1} & \hat{\mathbf{K}}_\eta^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{K}}_v \mathbf{L}'_3^{-1} & \hat{\mathbf{K}}_\eta^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{K}}_p \end{bmatrix}. \quad (40)$$

Therefore,

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_v(t) \\ \mathbf{x}_p(t) \\ \mathbf{x}_\eta(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{L}'_3^{-1} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \hat{\mathbf{K}}_\eta^{-1} & \hat{\mathbf{K}}_\eta^{-1} \hat{\mathbf{K}}_v \mathbf{L}'_3^{-1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{c}_d \\ \mathbf{c}_p \end{bmatrix}. \quad (41)$$

Since $\Delta \mathbf{p}(t) = \mathbf{x}_p(t)$ and $\mathbf{v}(t) = \hat{\mathbf{R}}^T \mathbf{x}_v(t)$, statements 1. and 2. are proven. \square

This lemma shows that the proposed control law provides robustness in the sense of Lemma 1: each vehicle rejects its own constant disturbance, and the distributed structure prevents constant disturbances acting on neighbouring vehicles from producing steady-state formation errors. From this control law, and using the construction in Madeiras, J., Cardeira, C. and Oliveira, P. (2024), the thrust magnitude and attitude reference required for trajectory tracking can be extracted. Let \mathbf{u}_i^* denote the input of the i -th vehicle calculated through the control law in (30). The following construction assumes that \mathbf{u}_i^* , $g\mathbf{e}_3$, and \mathbf{f}_D are expressed consistently in the inertial frame after the Lyapunov transformation. If \mathbf{u}_i^* satisfies

$$\|\mathbf{u}_i^*\| \leq \|g\mathbf{e}_3 + \mathbf{f}_D\|, \quad (42)$$

then the thrust magnitude can be obtained from

$$T_i = m \left| \sqrt{\|g\mathbf{e}_3 + \mathbf{f}_D\|^2 - \mathbf{u}_{i_1}^{*2} - \mathbf{u}_{i_2}^{*2} - \mathbf{u}_{i_3}^{*2}} \right|. \quad (43)$$

Furthermore, define

$$\mathbf{b}_3 = \frac{\mathbf{u}_i^* + \frac{T_i}{m} \mathbf{e}_3}{\|\mathbf{u}_i^* + \frac{T_i}{m} \mathbf{e}_3\|} \quad \mathbf{b}_2 = \frac{\mathbf{b}_3 \times \mathbf{e}_3}{\|\mathbf{b}_3 \times \mathbf{e}_3\|} \quad \mathbf{b}_1 = \frac{\mathbf{b}_2 \times \mathbf{b}_3}{\|\mathbf{b}_2 \times \mathbf{b}_3\|}$$

and set $\mathbf{R}_1 = [\mathbf{b}_1 \ \mathbf{b}_2 \ \mathbf{b}_3]$. Similarly, with $\vartheta \equiv g\mathbf{e}_3 + \mathbf{f}_D$ and $\mathbf{c}_d = [\cos \psi_d \ \sin \psi_d \ 0]^T$, where ψ_d is the desired yaw angle, define

$$\mathbf{c}_3 = \frac{\vartheta}{\|\vartheta\|} \quad \mathbf{c}_2 = \frac{\mathbf{c}_3 \times \mathbf{c}_d}{\|\mathbf{c}_3 \times \mathbf{c}_d\|} \quad \mathbf{c}_1 = \frac{\mathbf{c}_2 \times \mathbf{c}_3}{\|\mathbf{c}_2 \times \mathbf{c}_3\|}$$

and set $\mathbf{R}_2 = [\mathbf{c}_1 \ \mathbf{c}_2 \ \mathbf{c}_3]$. Then, the desired attitude for the i -th vehicle is given by

$$\mathbf{R}_{d_i} = \mathbf{R}_2 \mathbf{R}_1^T. \quad (44)$$

Define $\mathbf{W} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$. With

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W} \mathbf{R}_1^T \dot{\mathbf{b}}_3 \\ -\mathbf{b}_1^T \dot{\mathbf{b}}_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad \boldsymbol{\omega}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W} \mathbf{R}_2^T \dot{\mathbf{c}}_3 \\ -\mathbf{c}_1^T \dot{\mathbf{c}}_2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (45)$$

the desired angular velocity is computed by

$$\boldsymbol{\omega}_{d_i} = \mathbf{R}_1(\boldsymbol{\omega}_2 - \boldsymbol{\omega}_1). \quad (46)$$

The position controller therefore generates the thrust and attitude references required by the vehicle dynamics; the attitude controller is addressed next.

4.2 Attitude Tracking Control

The attitude controller is designed independently for each vehicle and closely follows the derivation in Madeiras, J., Carneira, C. and Oliveira, P. (2024). Suppose the desired attitude for the i -th vehicle is $\mathbf{q}_{d_i} = [\mathbf{q}_{0d_i}^T \ q_{0d_i}]^T$. The quaternion error may be defined as

$$\mathbf{e}_{q_i} = \boldsymbol{\Xi}^T(\mathbf{q}_{d_i}) \mathbf{q}_i, \quad (47)$$

with $\boldsymbol{\Xi}(\mathbf{q})$ defined as in (1). In the body frame, the angular velocity error can be written as

$$\mathbf{e}_{\omega_i} = \boldsymbol{\omega}_i - \mathbf{R}_{D_i}^B \boldsymbol{\omega}_{d_i}, \quad (48)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_{D_i}^B$ is the rotation matrix from the desired body frame to the actual body frame, which may be computed by

$$\mathbf{R}_{D_i}^B = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{q}_{d_i}^T \mathbf{q}_i \mathbf{I}_3 + [\mathbf{e}_{q_i} \times] \\ -\mathbf{e}_{q_i}^T \end{bmatrix}^T \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{q}_{d_i}^T \mathbf{q}_i \mathbf{I}_3 - [\mathbf{e}_{q_i} \times] \\ -\mathbf{e}_{q_i}^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (49)$$

Finally, introduce the integral state $\dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_i = \mathbf{e}_{q_i}$. From the system in (1) and differentiating equations (47) and (48), the following system is obtained,

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\mathbf{e}}_{q_i} = \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}(\mathbf{e}_{q_i}) \mathbf{e}_{\omega_i} \\ \dot{\mathbf{e}}_{\omega_i} = -\mathbf{J}^{-1}[\boldsymbol{\omega}_i \times] \mathbf{J} \boldsymbol{\omega}_i + \mathbf{J}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\tau}_i - \frac{d}{dt}(\mathbf{R}_{D_i}^B \boldsymbol{\omega}_{d_i}) \\ \dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_i = \mathbf{e}_{q_i} \end{cases}, \quad (50)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}(\mathbf{e}_{q_i}) = \mathbf{q}_{d_i}^T \mathbf{q}_i \mathbf{I}_3 + [\mathbf{e}_{q_i} \times]$. Define the modified input as

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_{n_i} = -\mathbf{J}^{-1}[\boldsymbol{\omega}_i \times] \mathbf{J} \boldsymbol{\omega}_i + \mathbf{J}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\tau}_i - \frac{d}{dt}(\mathbf{R}_{D_i}^B \boldsymbol{\omega}_{d_i}). \quad (51)$$

With the modified input, the equations can be written in state-space form,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{e}}_{q_i} \\ \dot{\mathbf{e}}_{\omega_i} \\ \dot{\boldsymbol{\xi}}_i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}(\mathbf{e}_{q_i}) & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{I}_3 & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{e}_{q_i} \\ \mathbf{e}_{\omega_i} \\ \boldsymbol{\xi}_i \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{I}_3 \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\tau}_{n_i}. \quad (52)$$

Consider the following coordinate transformation, proposed in Madeiras, J., Carneira, C. and Oliveira, P. (2024),

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_{q_i} \\ \mathbf{x}_{\omega_i} \\ \mathbf{x}_{\xi_i} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_3 & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \boldsymbol{\Sigma}(\mathbf{e}_{q_i}) & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{I}_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{e}_{q_i} \\ \mathbf{e}_{\omega_i} \\ \boldsymbol{\xi}_i \end{bmatrix}. \quad (53)$$

The determinant of $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}(\mathbf{e}_{q_i})$ is equal to $\mathbf{q}_{d_i}^T \mathbf{q}_i$, which can take any value in $[-1, 1]$. Since this transformation may fail to be invertible for some attitude configurations, it is not a Lyapunov transformation in the strict sense. The loss of invertibility occurs only when the relative rotation between the desired and actual attitudes is 180° . This singular set has measure zero; outside it, the matrix is continuous and has a continuous time derivative. Therefore, this coordinate transformation is treated as an *almost Lyapunov transformation*.

As in the position loop, this transformation only requires attitude measurements. Here, however, the determinant depends on the attitude error, so sensor noise affects the scaling between transformed and physical variables. A detailed analysis of this effect is outside the scope of this paper; the attitude measurements are assumed to be sufficiently accurate for the induced scaling error to be negligible.

The transformed system becomes

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{x}}_{q_i} \\ \dot{\mathbf{x}}_{\omega_i} \\ \dot{\mathbf{x}}_{\xi_i} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{I}_3 & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{I}_3 & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_{q_i} \\ \mathbf{x}_{\omega_i} \\ \mathbf{x}_{\xi_i} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{I}_3 \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\tau}_i, \quad (54)$$

where

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_i = \boldsymbol{\Sigma}(\mathbf{e}_{q_i}) \boldsymbol{\tau}_{n_i} + \dot{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}(\mathbf{e}_{q_i}) \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1}(\mathbf{e}_{q_i}) \mathbf{x}_{\omega_i}. \quad (55)$$

A control law of the form $\boldsymbol{\tau}_i = -\mathbf{K}_{q_i} \mathbf{x}_{q_i} - \mathbf{K}_{\omega_i} \mathbf{x}_{\omega_i} - \mathbf{K}_{\xi_i} \mathbf{x}_{\xi_i}$ renders system (54) globally exponentially stable and, consequently, system (52) exponentially stable on the domain where the almost Lyapunov transformation is nonsingular. In fact, with that control law, the eigenvalues of (54) are the solutions of

$$\det \left(\lambda^3 \mathbf{I}_3 + \lambda^2 \mathbf{K}_{\omega_i} + \frac{\lambda}{2} \mathbf{K}_{q_i} + \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{K}_{\xi_i} \right) = 0. \quad (56)$$

In particular, because the motion along the three axes is decoupled, the gain matrices can be diagonal and, in that case, the eigenvalues are guaranteed to lie in the open left half-plane if and only if $k_{\omega_j}, k_{q_j}, k_{\xi_j} > 0$ and $k_{\omega_j} k_{q_j} > k_{\xi_j}$, for all $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$.

With a stable control law $\boldsymbol{\tau}_{i_i}^*$, applying the reverse transformations leads to

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}_i^* = [\boldsymbol{\omega}_i \times] \mathbf{J} \boldsymbol{\omega}_i + \mathbf{J} \frac{d}{dt}(\mathbf{R}_{D_i}^B \boldsymbol{\omega}_{d_i}) + \mathbf{J} \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1}(\mathbf{e}_{q_i}) \left(\boldsymbol{\tau}_{i_i}^* - \dot{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}(\mathbf{e}_{q_i}) \mathbf{e}_{\omega_i} \right). \quad (57)$$

This completes the controller construction.

5. SIMULATION RESULTS

5.1 Parameter configuration

To corroborate the theoretical findings, this section presents simulation results for a representative case. Five identical quadrotors are simulated, each with a mass of $m_i = 0.5$ kg and an inertia matrix of $\mathbf{J}_i = \text{diag}(0.0027, 0.0029, 0.0053)$ kg.m². It is assumed that information flows among the vehicles as shown in Fig. 2, with an adjacency matrix

$$\mathbf{A} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (58)$$

The vehicles must maintain a V-formation aligned with the yaw of the first quadrotor, as shown in the same figure, with a minimum vehicle separation of 1 m and an aperture angle of 60° . Furthermore, only vehicle 1 will receive information about the reference trajectory, with a gain $b_1 = 1.5$.

Fig. 2. Formation Diagram

The five drones start at, respectively, positions $\mathbf{p}_{01} = [-2 \ 3 \ 0]^T$ m, $\mathbf{p}_{02} = [2 \ -4 \ 0]^T$ m, $\mathbf{p}_{03} = [2 \ 2 \ 0]^T$ m, $\mathbf{p}_{04} = [0 \ 0 \ 0]^T$ m and $\mathbf{p}_{05} = [1 \ 1 \ 0]^T$ m. At $t = 2$ s, the vehicles start to climb to a height of 2 m while going into formation. Starting at $t = 10$ s, the reference trajectory to be followed by the formation is represented, in the x - y plane, in Fig. 3, beginning in the origin, at a constant height of 2 m and a constant velocity of 0.5 m/s. The yaw reference aligns the front of the vehicles with the reference velocity vector. Constant wind perturbations are applied

Fig. 3. Reference trajectory in the X - Y plane

at specified time instants and maintained until the end of the simulation to verify disturbance rejection. Starting at $t = 40$ s, drone 1 is subjected to a constant perturbation $d_1 = [2 \ 0 \ -2]^T$. At $t = 80$ s, drone 2 is subjected to a constant perturbation $d_2 = [0 \ -2.5 \ 0]^T$ and drone 3 to a perturbation $d_3 = [0 \ 2.5 \ 0]^T$. Finally, at $t = 100$ s, drone 4 is subjected to a perturbation $d_4 = [2 \ -1.5 \ 1.5]^T$ and drone 5 to $d_5 = [-2 \ 1.5 \ 1.5]^T$. Additional wind gusts are also generated using the Dryden model with a low-altitude wind speed of 4 m/s, to assess the robustness of the proposed solution.

Each vehicle will have the same set of gains defined as $\mathbf{K}_{v_i} = \text{diag}(4, 4, 4)$, $\mathbf{K}_{p_i} = \text{diag}(6, 6, 6)$, and $\mathbf{K}_{\eta_i} = \text{diag}(4, 4, 4)$, using the notation of the previous section. For the individual attitude controllers, the gains are $\mathbf{K}_{\omega_i} = \text{diag}(32, 32, 32)$, $\mathbf{K}_{q_i} = \text{diag}(490, 490, 490)$ and $\mathbf{K}_{\xi_i} =$

$\text{diag}(1805, 1805, 1805)$. The attitude controller is selected sufficiently fast not to introduce significant delay in the position loop. These gains also satisfy the stability conditions stated in the previous section. In a final numerical validation, the eigenvalues of the pinned Laplacian \mathbf{L}' and the maximum required thrust are also reported to make the stability and feasibility checks explicit.

The drag force acting on each vehicle is modelled as

$$\mathbf{f}_{D_i} = -\frac{1}{2m_i}\rho\|\mathbf{v}_i\|\mathbf{v}_i C_{D_i}, \quad (59)$$

with $\rho = 1.225 \text{ kg/m}^3$ denoting the air density and C_{D_i} the vehicle drag coefficient. A model mismatch between the controller and the real world is simulated by making $C_{D_{real}} = 0.002$ and $C_{D_{model}} = 0.001$. To evaluate performance under sensor imperfections, white noise is added to the position measurements of every drone, with standard deviation 15 cm in each coordinate, together with a delay of 10 ms. The velocity measurements also include white noise with standard deviation 15 cm/s. Figures 4 and 5 show the tracking errors and the attitude, represented by Tait-Bryan angles describing an intrinsic zyx rotation for better interpretation. The yaw angle is compared with the prescribed heading reference.

Fig. 4. Position tracking errors

5.2 Discussion of results

Figure 4 supports three conclusions consistent with Lemma 1. First, the closed-loop system is stable. Second, it tracks the reference with null steady-state error on the straight segments of the path. Third, constant wind disturbances do not introduce bias in the tracking errors. This is especially clear for $t > 200$ s, where all vehicles are subject to constant winds but the errors remain around zero in all axes. The turbulent gusts, drag-model mismatch

Fig. 5. Attitude of the vehicles

and sensor noise have only mild effects on the performance, which suggests good robustness even without state or disturbance estimators.

Figure 5 is consistent with this conclusion: yaw errors remain small, while pitch and roll stay within satisfactory bounds. The non-zero pitch and roll offsets show how the vehicles compensate the constant wind components, thereby avoiding bias in the position errors. The effect of noise is more visible in the attitude variables because of the fast attitude loop. As a final remark, the simulations also indicate that the formation performance improves when the communication graph becomes denser, as expected. In the present configuration, vehicle 1 must compromise between following the trajectory and remaining close to its neighbours; this compromise is tuned through the virtual-drone weights in L' .

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6. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a non-linear distributed control strategy for quadrotor formations, extendable to multi-agent systems. The proposed methodology drives agents to consensus on selected states over strongly connected topologies. This is possible for general non-linear node dynamics, provided that individual systems have sufficient stability margin to compensate for destabilizing modes

introduced by the outer loop. For n identical quadrotors, the distributed controller ensures stability, rejection of constant wind disturbances, and null steady-state error for constant-velocity trajectories. Lyapunov transformations recast the dynamics as linear time-invariant systems without approximation, enabling linear design tools inside a non-linear controller. Simulations confirm the expected behaviour under noise, modelling errors, delays and wind disturbances, without estimators. Future work should include experimental validation, actuator-saturation analysis and estimators for stronger sensing limitations.

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